

Breaking the Glass Scalpel: Examining the Barriers and Enablers of Women's Leadership Advancement in Nigeria's Healthcare Sector

Moradeke Atoki

&

Omolade Osibogun

Abstract

This study investigated the structural, cultural, and institutional factors influencing women's advancement into leadership roles within Nigeria's healthcare sector. Employing a cross sectional survey design the data was collected from 292 female healthcare professionals across primary healthcare centers and the directorate of health. A structured questionnaire, developed using the role congruity theory and validated through a pilot study captured participants' demographic characteristics, leadership experiences, perceived barriers, and opportunities for advancement. Descriptive statistics and multiple logistic regression analyses were conducted using SPSS. The findings revealed that out of the 292 participants only 13.4% had received leadership training, while 27.1% had held leadership positions, primarily as heads of hospitals and primary healthcare units (72.2%). Among those with leadership experience, 92.4% evaluated their experience positively. Nearly half of the participants (45.2%) had observed a female leader in their workplace and rated the experience positively, with 13.4% reporting a negative experience. More than half (58.6%) expressed readiness to assume leadership positions. A majority of participants (69.5%) perceived women as successful leaders, 64.7% supported women in leadership roles, and 80.1% believed women possess adequate self-confidence for leadership. Most participants (74.6%) identified leadership training programs as a key opportunity for women to assume leadership positions. The multivariate analysis showed that postgraduate education [OR=2.74, 95% CI 1.18–6.35], working in the health directorate [OR=4.96, 95% CI 1.97–12.46], and receiving leadership training [OR=6.12, 95% CI 2.83–13.23] were independently associated with women taking on leadership roles. The findings underscore a growing acceptance of female leadership in Nigeria's healthcare system, while highlighting the need for structured development programs, institutional reforms, and gender-sensitive policies. Addressing entrenched social norms and strengthening professional support mechanisms are critical for breaking the "glass scalpel" and enhancing women's representation in executive healthcare leadership.

Keywords

Women in leadership; Healthcare sector; Leadership advancement; Role Congruity Theory; Work-life balance; Leadership training; Glass ceiling.

1. Background of the Study

Leadership within the healthcare sector plays a pivotal role in shaping the quality, accessibility, and effectiveness of health service delivery. However, despite the increasing participation of women in healthcare professions globally yet their representation in leadership positions remains disproportionately low. This disparity is often referred to as the “glass ceiling” phenomenon which is a metaphor describing the invisible barriers that prevent women from advancing into top leadership roles despite having the requisite qualifications and experience (Grant, 2025).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) report on value gender and equity in the global health workforce it was accounted that women comprise approximately 70% of the global health workforce but thus far deep seated disparities in leadership and decision making power persist as women only occupy 25% of leadership positions (Smith et al, 2025). Furthermore, although there has been a gradual increase in women occupying leadership positions within major global health organizations, these roles are predominantly filled by women from the developed nations. In contrast, women occupying leadership position from low- and middle-income countries still remain significant low (Zeinali et al., 2021). To buttress this point earlier findings from Dhatt et al (2021) and the World Health Organization (WHO) report revealed that 75% of global health leaders are men and these barriers persist despite global and national calls for gender equity in leadership, including the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5), which advocates for women’s full participation in leadership and decision-making across all sectors (United Nations Sustainable Development Goals). The failure to address these issues has broader implications: leadership imbalance in healthcare affects policy responsiveness, workplace inclusivity, and overall health system performance.

Multiple challenges faced by female global health professionals includes: the struggle to synchronize leadership responsibilities with reproductive timelines, the demands of extensive travel, and the difficulties of balancing family life with globally distributed assignments. Similarly, a global study conducted during the 2017 Women Leaders in Global Health Conference identified critical barriers to women’s leadership advancement such as inadequate mentorship, gender bias, limited confidence, and the difficulty of balancing professional and domestic responsibilities (Eaton et al., 2020). Extensive research further emphasizes recurring global challenges confronting women in health leadership which includes: the scarcity of female mentors and role models, sexual harassment, reproductive-related discrimination, implicit and explicit biases affecting promotions, salaries and research grants. While the global underrepresentation of women in health leadership is well-documented, country-specific evidence particularly concerning barriers to women’s leadership in the health sectors of low and middle income nations including Nigeria remains insufficient and calls for deeper empirical investigation (Saville et al., 2024).

Globally, women in healthcare face similar barriers, including stereotyping, unequal pay, and limited professional networks (Zeinali et al. 2021). However, in Nigeria, these challenges are intensified by societal expectations that place domestic responsibilities primarily on women,

thereby restricting their ability to pursue demanding leadership careers (Adeoti, 2025). Moreover, patriarchal structures and traditional gender norms often dictate leadership selection processes, favoring men over women irrespective of competence or merit (Olutayo, 2024). Such systemic barriers not only impede gender equity but also limit the diversity of perspectives critical to effective healthcare leadership.

In Nigeria, this challenge is particularly pronounced within the healthcare sector, where women constitute a substantial portion of the workforce but remain underrepresented in decision-making and executive positions (Agubuzo, 2024). Despite the growing number of women entering the healthcare workforce in Nigeria, their representation in senior leadership and decision-making positions remains disproportionately low. Women dominate frontline and mid-level healthcare roles such as nursing, midwifery, and administration; however, they are markedly underrepresented in strategic leadership positions such as hospital directors, deans of medical schools, chief medical officers, and policymakers (Balogun, 2022). This persistent gender disparity reflects what scholars describe as the “glass scalpel” which is an invisible barrier that limits women’s upward mobility in health leadership despite their qualifications and contributions (Richards, 2017).

The problem lies not in the absence of capable women, but in the systemic, cultural, and institutional barriers that hinder their advancement. Socio-cultural expectations, gender stereotypes, unequal access to leadership training, limited mentorship, and gender bias in recruitment and promotion practices continue to impede women’s professional growth (Ughasoro et al., 2022). Furthermore, patriarchal norms in Nigeria’s society reinforce perceptions that leadership is a masculine domain, marginalizing women from key decision-making spaces in healthcare governance (Ajibade et al., 2021).

Therefore, there is a critical need to examine both the barriers and enablers of women’s leadership advancement in Nigeria’s healthcare sector. Understanding these dynamics will not only inform gender-responsive leadership development strategies but also contribute to building equitable health institutions that reflect the diversity of the workforce they represent (Mousa et al., 2022). Understanding the interplay between barriers and enablers is essential for fostering women’s leadership advancement in Nigeria’s healthcare sector (Jrasat et al., 2024). By examining both structural and individual-level factors, this study seeks to contribute to ongoing discourse on gender equality in leadership, offering practical insights for policymakers, healthcare institutions, and advocacy groups working toward a more inclusive and equitable healthcare system.

2. Literature Review

According to Desai et al. (2016), women working in healthcare continue to encounter numerous challenges stemming from unfavorable work environments. These include gender-based pay disparities, poor working conditions, limited career advancement opportunities, work related stress and institutional policies that reinforce patriarchal norms. Desai et al. (2016), further observed that women in the United States earned significantly less than their male counterparts despite possessing comparable qualifications, experience, and productivity levels. For instance, female nurses have frequently reported working in unsupportive environments that offer minimal prospects for professional growth, while also facing difficulties in balancing work and family responsibilities. These factors often impede their career progression and contribute to heightened stress and fatigue (Younas et al 2014., Kerr et al 2016). Additionally, a systematic review examining gender disparities in surgical skill acquisition found that such differences were more evident among medical students (Ali et al., 2015). Their study suggested that future surgical training programs should incorporate more personalized learning approaches including mentorship and one on one coaching to better support the development of female physicians (Ali et al., 2015).

Shagun et al. (2023). opined that although women comprise an estimated 70–75% of the global health workforce, significant disparities in power and leadership positions persist. They further asserted that limited evidence exists on the specific factors that enable or hinder women working in public health in India, and how these compare to experiences in other regions. To address this gap, the study gathered and analyzed insights from women working in public health in India, East Africa (Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda), and in global health settings (Canada and the United States). The goal was to identify and compare the unique enablers and barriers influencing women's professional experiences and leadership development across these contexts. Common themes emerged across all regions, highlighting both enabling factors such as access to mentors, professional networks, and leadership rooted in empathy and collaboration and impeding factors, including overt bias and family related responsibilities. However, the ways in which these factors influence women's leadership trajectories vary in important ways between India and other regions. While women in India share many of the same enablers and challenges as their counterparts elsewhere, there are distinct contextual differences that shape their professional advancement. Developing targeted institutional programs and policies to address these factors can help foster an equitable and supportive professional environment for women in health and related sectors.

Tlaiss (2013), stated that despite global efforts to promote gender equality, women remain significantly underrepresented in management positions, and little is known about their experiences in the healthcare sectors of developing nations. To address this gap, their study examined the barriers that hinder and the enablers that support women's career advancement within this context. Adopting a relational approach that integrates macro (socio-cultural), meso (organizational), and micro (individual) levels of analysis, this study is guided by institutional theory and grounded in social constructionism. Using a qualitative research design, in-depth semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted with women managers from various healthcare occupations and managerial levels in Lebanon. A combination of purposive and snowball sampling techniques was employed and data were analyzed thematically to identify emerging patterns and

themes. Findings highlight the persistence of discriminatory cultural norms, gendered social roles, and expectations that act as significant barriers to women's career progression. The study also reveals how societal gender stereotypes and expectations spill over into organizational structures and attitudes, reinforcing systemic barriers in the workplace. At the same time, women demonstrate agency and resilience, navigating patriarchal norms and organizational discrimination to advance their careers. The interplay between macro- and meso-level factors underscores the importance of individual agency as a critical enabler of women's professional growth. This study contributes new insights into the under-researched experiences of women in the Middle Eastern healthcare sector. It emphasizes the central role of women's agency in shaping their career trajectories and argues that understanding the complexity of women's career development requires a relational and intersectional approach which is one that considers the dynamic interactions among gender, agency, socio-cultural realities, and organizational contexts.

Chanda et al (2024), explored the persistent challenges that hinder women's advancement into leadership roles. Conducted in the Lusaka District the capital city of Zambia the research involved participants drawn from six organizations, comprising three private and three government institutions. Through an extensive review of existing literature and empirical evidence, the study identifies the major barriers that impede women's progression into leadership positions across multiple sectors. The study revealed that deep-rooted societal attitudes continue to favor men in leadership positions. Both explicit and implicit biases contribute to discriminatory practices in recruitment, promotion, and performance evaluations. Additionally, women were found to have unequal access to opportunities for advancement, such as high-profile projects, stretch assignments, and sponsorship from senior leaders. These limitations restrict the development of critical skills and experiences necessary for leadership roles.

Alobaid et al (2020), opined that over the past few decades the number of women entering the global medical and healthcare workforce has risen significantly. Women now hold diverse roles across healthcare institutions, hospitals, and educational settings. Despite this progress, female healthcare professionals continue to encounter persistent challenges in their workplaces. Their scoping review sought to identify and examine the key difficulties faced by women in the healthcare sector. Their review employed Arksey and O'Malley's six-step framework to systematically identify and map the existing literature on the challenges encountered by female healthcare professionals. Databases searched included Embase, EmCare, Medline, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), and Business Source Complete (BSC). Additional searches were conducted through Google Scholar, Trove, and relevant grey literature sources. The results revealed that three central themes emerged from the synthesis: (i) family responsibilities, (ii) workplace environment, and (iii) gender stereotyping. The findings indicate that female healthcare professionals continue to face multifaceted challenges that affect both their family lives and workplace experiences. These include balancing domestic responsibilities, navigating unsupportive work environments, and confronting gender-based stereotypes. The study recommends that to promote gender equity in healthcare organizations, strategies such as flexible scheduling, reduced work hours, and part-time employment opportunities should be implemented to better support women in balancing their professional and personal roles.

Maheshwari et al (2023), sought to uncover the factors that motivate women to pursue leadership positions and to determine whether they continue to encounter barriers within higher education institutions (HEIs). Their study involved 22 female participants from HEIs in Mexico and adopted a qualitative narrative research design to explore the enablers and obstacles experienced by Mexican female academics. Findings revealed four primary barriers and four significant enablers influencing women's career growth and leadership advancement. A deeper understanding of these factors provides valuable insights into how culturally sensitive developmental relationships can help women overcome existing challenges. Additionally, the study offers implications for human resource development initiatives aimed at fostering women's leadership in academia.

Saville et al (2024), examined the enablers and barriers affecting gender equality and the effectiveness of organizational interventions that can promote women's leadership. They conducted a systematic search across JSTOR, PubMed, SCOPUS, and Web of Science databases, as well as Google Scholar and reference lists of selected articles. The inclusion criteria covered studies published in English between 2000 and 2022 in peer-reviewed journals or grey literature, focusing on paid, formal health professionals and addressing factors influencing women's representation or leadership. A total of 26 studies were reviewed comprising of 15 from India and 11 from Kenya with seven from each country focusing specifically on nursing. Participants included both male and female health sector workers. Among the studies, seven employed mixed methods, 11 were qualitative, five were quantitative, and three were commentaries. At the individual and interpersonal levels, factors influencing women's career progression included family support, personal competencies (knowledge and skills), and access to material resources. At the organizational level, key factors were capacity building, networking opportunities, workplace policies, gender quotas, organizational culture, flexibility, and workload. Nursing-specific studies also identified issues such as verbal and sexual harassment and rigid professional hierarchies as significant barriers. Structural barriers included limited infrastructure, inadequate training institutions, and poor working conditions. Normative barriers reflected entrenched gender norms, occupational segregation (especially in nursing), and the disproportionate burden of unpaid care work on women. Women working in India and Kenya's health sectors encounter numerous challenges that hinder their career growth and leadership advancement. Addressing these issues requires gender-transformative approaches including anti-discrimination and anti-harassment measures, targeted mentorship and leadership training, improved parental benefits, flexible or remote work options, enhanced family and coworker support, and robust equal-opportunity policies and legislation.

Ayisha et al (2024), conducted an extensive review of both academic and governmental (grey) literature on women's career development focusing on the enablers and challenges influencing access to senior leadership positions within the Ghanaian context. The review was organized thematically around predetermined and emerging topics related to career development, gender, and leadership progression. Searches were carried out across major academic databases including Google Scholar, Springer, ScienceDirect, Emerald, ProQuest, Sage, and Web of Science, using

keywords such as leadership roles, career development obstacles, and facilitators. The findings of their study revealed that the major barriers to women's professional advancement include limited social networking opportunities, personal constraints, work-life imbalance, and negative perceptions of female leaders by subordinates. Conversely, factors such as sustained family and mentor support, evolving employer attitudes, and women's demonstrated leadership competence serve as key enablers driving their career progression and leadership success.

Kelly (2019), stated that female participation and representation in Nigerian politics remain considerably low. They opine that the principal factors hindering women's political participation include: the absence of decisive government action; Lower educational and employment opportunities for women; Enduring sexist beliefs rooted in religious or traditional customs; A corrupt, male-dominated, and patronage-based political system; Election-related violence, including targeted attacks on female candidates. They further stated that although Nigeria has ratified several international conventions and adopted national gender policies to enhance women's representation, implementation remains weak. The study revealed that government published data between 1999 and 2019 reveal consistently low female representation in elected offices. Scholarly discourse largely emphasizes structural and cultural barriers such as the political party system, the influence of corruption, conservative gender norms, and the use of hate speech and violence to intimidate women. Comparative insights from other Sub-Saharan African countries offer valuable lessons. For instance, Rwanda's remarkable success in achieving high female representation and South Africa's adoption of gender quotas highlight actionable strategies Nigeria could emulate. Nonetheless, while numerous civil society organizations advocate for increased women's political participation, many of their publications are descriptive rather than evaluative, lacking comprehensive assessments of which interventions are most effective in achieving gender parity in governance.

Harrison et al (2022), synthesize and present key themes from two working group sessions focused on developing strategies to enhance women's leadership training and opportunities in global health. A total of 182 women professionals in global health participated in two virtual working group sessions organized by the Johns Hopkins Center for Global Health via Zoom. Participants were divided into breakout rooms to discuss pre-assigned topics concerning women's leadership in global health. Their analysis revealed two primary themes crucial to the success of emerging women leaders in global health. The first emphasized the importance of acquiring essential individual skills necessary for career advancement. The second highlighted the need for institutional environments that support, encourage, and enable women to assume and thrive in leadership positions. They further stated that investing in women's leadership potential can generate positive outcomes for individuals, institutions, and communities alike. This study provides actionable insights and recommendations to promote women's advancement in global health by strengthening personal competencies and creating supportive institutional structures where female leaders can grow and excel.

Adekunle et al (2024), explored the challenges and opportunities associated with advancing women into leadership positions within Nigerian corporate governance. Their research focuses on the major factors that hinder women's ascent into corporate leadership roles particularly cultural norms, organizational policies, and access to professional networks. Using a qualitative research design, the study draws on in-depth interviews with female executives across various industries in Nigeria. These narratives provide critical insights into how cultural expectations, entrenched biases, and institutional practices influence women's leadership journeys. The study also investigates how restricted access to mentorship and professional networks and key drivers of career progression which further limits women's advancement opportunities. Their findings indicate that although some progress has been made toward improving women's representation in corporate leadership, persistent cultural and structural barriers continue to obstruct meaningful advancement. Nonetheless, the study identifies promising strategies for progress, including the establishment of structured mentorship programs and the promotion of inclusive organizational cultures that actively value and advance gender diversity. Their research underscores the importance of a strategic and sustained approach to dismantling these barriers and offers practical and actionable recommendations for corporate leaders and policymakers dedicated to empowering women in leadership.

Hayden et al (2018), explored the existing roles and perspectives of professionals working within the Vector Control (VC) sector across Kenya, Indonesia, India, and other countries. Their study identified key barriers limiting women's pursuit of leadership positions in the VC field including low awareness of career opportunities, cultural constraints, and the prevailing perception that VC is traditionally a male-dominated occupation. Addressing these challenges requires targeted strategies such as strengthening education and recruitment campaigns, expanding access to higher education, and developing structured mentorship programs. Interestingly the result of their study revealed that female respondents were nearly six times more likely to report being encouraged to pursue leadership roles within their organizations compared to their male counterparts (odds ratio = 5.9, $P > 0.03$, 95% confidence interval: 1.19–29.42). This suggests that once women enter the VC workforce, they experience relatively limited discrimination and enjoy enhanced prospects for leadership advancement.

3. Methods

Study Design

This cross-sectional study adopted a survey research design and was conducted across health facilities which includes: primary healthcare centers, hospitals and the Directorate of Health in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Nigeria. The cross sectional approach provided a snapshot of women's leadership experiences at a specific point in time thereby offering valuable insights into their challenges and opportunities.

The study encompassed three categories of healthcare institutions in FCT which includes primary healthcare centers, public hospitals and the Directorate of Health. The sample size was notably larger in hospitals compared to the Directorate of Health and primary healthcare centers. The structural design of hospitals tends to vary according to departmental diversity whereas primary healthcare centers generally exhibit simpler architectural layouts. In terms of leadership dynamics shows that the organizational structure and environment of the Directorate of Health appear to provide greater opportunities for women to attain leadership positions compared to other healthcare settings.

Sampling Method and Sample Size

A random sample of female healthcare professionals was drawn from various healthcare institutions in FCT including hospitals, primary healthcare centers, and the Directorate of Health.

From each selected institution, the complete list of female healthcare staff was used to identify participants through systematic random sampling, employing a random starting point and fixed intervals. The number of participants chosen from each facility was proportionate to the size of its female workforce. No stratification was applied to staff lists. In cases where a selected individual was unavailable or declined participation then the next eligible person on the list was chosen. This sampling procedure was consistently applied across all institutions.

A total of 292 female health professionals including those in leadership and management positions were invited to take part in the study. Data were collected from randomly selected hospitals, primary healthcare centers and the Directorate of Health. Of the 308 invited participants, 5% did not respond primarily due to lack of interest or motivation to complete the questionnaire consequently 292 responses were analyzed.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria encompassed all female employees working in healthcare settings, irrespective of their roles, designations, or employment status. Participants aged 18 years and above were eligible, including full-time, part-time, and contract staff. All women employed within the healthcare sector were included regardless of whether they held leadership positions. This broad inclusion approach was adopted to provide a comprehensive understanding of the general workplace environment.

Exclusion criteria included individuals on maternity leave at the commencement of the study and employees on extended sick leave.

Study Tool and Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was designed following an extensive literature review and expert consultation. Its development was guided by the Role Congruity Theory of Prejudice Toward Female Leaders. The instrument consisted of five sections:

1. Demographic and professional information,
2. Leadership experience,
3. Perceptions of women in leadership roles,
4. Barriers to women attaining leadership positions, and
5. Opportunities for women in leadership.

The questionnaire included multiple-choice, short-answer, and Likert-scale questions. The Likert scales ranged from strongly disagree to strongly agree when assessing opinions on leadership and barriers, and from unimportant to extremely important for evaluating opportunities. Leadership experience was assessed through questions on prior leadership training, current or previous leadership positions and the duration of leadership involvement.

The study's independent variables were participants' sociodemographic and professional characteristics, while the dependent variables included both the positive and negative impacts of leadership roles on female healthcare staff such as professional advancement, family and social life, and leadership-related challenges including work-life balance, the "queen bee" phenomenon, and cultural constraints.

The study further explored available opportunities such as leadership commitment and training initiatives. Prior to full deployment, the questionnaire underwent a pilot test to evaluate its validity and reliability. The pilot test conducted with 15 participants and the pilot study identified issues related to structure and clarity including a lack of thematic organization and the use of complex language. Based on these findings and expert feedback, the questionnaire was revised to improve its structure, simplify the language and enhance overall clarity. Participants responded positively by noting that the revised version was easier to understand and complete. The pilot study produced a Cronbach's alpha of 0.74, indicating acceptable internal consistency, and a reliability coefficient of 0.82, confirming the instrument's reliability.

Data collection commenced following formal authorization from the General Directorate of Health which granted access to health facilities and permitted staff participation. Participants were invited to complete the self-administered questionnaire in English language. The researcher clearly explained the study's objectives and significance and provided detailed instructions for completing the questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Multiple logistic regression analysis was conducted to account for potential factors related to occupying a leadership position. Since the primary outcome variable which is leadership status was binary in nature (Yes/No) thereby warranting that logistic regression model is most appropriate. The results were presented as adjusted odds ratios (AORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

Ethical Consideration

Prior to completing the questionnaire, all participants provided written informed consent. The research procedures were conducted in full compliance with applicable ethical guidelines and regulations.

4. Results

Demographics and Career Background

Table 1. Sociodemographic and Professional Characteristics of the Study Participants

Characteristic	No (%)
Age groups (years)	
≤30	61 (20.9)
31–40	135 (46.2)
>40	96 (32.9)
Marital status	
Single	79 (27.1)
Married	204 (69.9)
Widow/divorced	9 (3.1)
Have children (n = 261)	
Yes	236 (90.4)
No	25 (9.6)
Number of children (n = 236)	
1–2	123 (52.1)
3	71 (30.1)
4–6	42 (17.8)
Highest level of education	
Nursing secondary school or institute diploma	113 (38.7)
Bachelor's degree	149 (51.0)
Postgraduate degree	30 (10.3)
Profession	

Characteristic	No (%)
Physician/Dentist/Pharmacist	127 (43.5)
Nurse/Medical assistant/Lab staff	140 (48.0)
Other	25 (8.6)
Work setting	
Directorate of health	33 (11.3)
Hospital	187 (64.0)
Primary healthcare center	72 (24.7)
Work experience (years)	
≤5	50 (17.1)
6–10	46 (15.8)
11–15	88 (30.1)
>15	108 (37.0)

A total of 292 women participated in the survey out of 305 female health worker staffs. The age ranged from 19–60 years, with nearly half of the respondents aged between 31–40 years (46.2%). The majority were married (69.9%), and most had children (90.4%), with over half (52.1%) reporting one to two children.

In terms of education, most respondents held a bachelor’s degree (51.0%), followed by nursing or institute diplomas (38.7%). The largest professional group consisted of nurses and medical assistants (48.0%), while 64.0% were employed in governmental hospitals.

The average work experience was 14.6 ± 8.8 years (range: 1–44 years), with 37.0% of participants having more than 15 years of professional experience, reflecting a well-established and experienced healthcare workforce (Table 1).

Table 2. Leadership Experience and Experience with Women in Leadership Positions (n = 292)

Variable	No (%)
Received any leadership training	39 (13.4)
Being in any leadership position	79 (27.1)
Currently in leadership position (n = 79)	41 (51.9)
Leadership position held (n = 79)	
Director in the health directorate	12 (15.2)
Admin director	2 (2.5)
Director of primary healthcare center	8 (10.1)
Head of unit in hospital or primary healthcare center	57 (72.2)
Leadership experience (years) (n = 79)	
≤5	39 (49.4)
6–10	19 (24.1)
>10	21 (26.6)
Evaluation of own leadership experience (n = 79)	
Positive	73 (92.4)
Negative	1 (1.3)
Not sure	5 (6.3)
Experienced a woman as leader in the workplace	247 (84.6)
Experience with having women in leadership	
Positive	132 (45.2)
Negative	39 (13.4)
No difference	80 (27.4)

Variable	No (%)
Not sure	41 (14.0)
Women can be successful in leadership roles	
Yes	235 (80.5)
No	23 (7.9)
Not sure	34 (11.6)
Readiness to take leadership position	
Yes	171 (58.6)
No	62 (21.2)
Not sure	59 (20.2)

Leadership Background

Out of 292 participants only 13.4% reported having received leadership training, yet 27.1% had held leadership positions mostly as heads of units in hospitals or healthcare centers (72.2%). Among those who had leadership roles, 51.9% were still currently serving in such positions. The mean \pm SD leadership experience was 8.3 ± 8.1 years (range: 1–35 years), with nearly half (49.4%) having five years or less of leadership experience.

A large majority (92.4%) described their leadership experience as positive. Additionally, 84.6% of participants had previously worked under a female leader, and 45.2% viewed that experience positively. Most respondents believed that women can succeed in leadership roles (80.5%), and over half (58.6%) expressed readiness to take on leadership positions in the future, as shown in Table 2.

Table 3. Study Participants’ Opinions About Women in Leadership Positions (n = 292)

Statement	Strongly Disagree N(%)	Disagree N(%)	Neutral N(%)	Agree N(%)	Strongly Agree N(%)	Not Sure N(%)
Women are successful in leadership positions	15 (5.1)	17 (5.8)	35 (12.0)	135 (46.2)	68 (23.3)	22 (7.5)
Having a woman in a leadership position is acceptable by employees	13 (4.4)	25 (8.6)	44 (15.1)	155 (53.1)	34 (11.6)	21 (7.2)
Female leaders usually undermine or criticize other women	27 (9.2)	80 (27.4)	46 (15.8)	81 (27.7)	19 (6.5)	39 (13.4)
Women in leadership positions can give enough time and effort to the work	14 (4.8)	33 (11.3)	37 (12.7)	142 (48.6)	46 (15.8)	20 (6.8)

Women in Leadership

The majority of participants expressed positive attitudes toward women in leadership roles. About 69.5% agreed or strongly agreed that women are successful leaders, while 64.7% believed that female leadership is widely accepted by employees. Similarly, 64.4% affirmed that women in leadership positions can devote sufficient time and effort to their work, reflecting strong confidence in women’s managerial commitment and capability.

However, 33.9% of respondents agreed that female leaders might sometimes undermine or criticize other women, suggesting that perceptions of internal competition or “queen bee” behavior persist among a minority of respondents. Overall, the results indicate growing acceptance of women’s leadership competence and contribution within the healthcare sector (Table 3).

Table 4: Factors Acting as Barriers for Women to Take Leadership/Management Positions

Statement	Strongly Disagree N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Agree N(%)	Strongly Agree N (%)	Not Sure N(%)
The family/husband supports women to be in leadership positions	28 (9.6)	36 (12.3)	35 (12.0)	121 (41.4)	42 (14.4)	30 (10.3)
The society supports women to be in leadership positions	31 (10.6)	69 (23.6)	34 (11.6)	93 (31.8)	20 (6.8)	45 (15.4)
The ministry or organization encourages women to take leadership positions	20 (6.8)	41 (14.0)	46 (15.8)	130 (44.5)	19 (6.5)	36 (12.3)
Women in leadership positions can maintain a healthy work–life balance	18 (6.2)	33 (11.3)	36 (12.3)	128 (43.8)	54 (18.5)	23 (7.9)
Care for family and children is an important barrier for women to take a leadership role	14 (4.8)	46 (15.8)	20 (6.8)	145 (49.7)	47 (16.1)	20 (6.8)
Women have leadership skills and abilities to be successful in leadership positions	12 (4.1)	15 (5.1)	16 (5.5)	157 (53.8)	76 (26.0)	16 (5.5)

Statement	Strongly Disagree N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Agree N(%)	Strongly Agree N (%)	Not Sure N(%)
Women are too emotional to be in leadership positions	49 (16.8)	106 (36.3)	34 (11.6)	58 (19.9)	14 (4.8)	31 (10.6)
Women have the required strong personality to be in leadership positions	15 (5.1)	11 (3.8)	19 (6.5)	161 (55.1)	70 (24.0)	16 (5.5)
Women can have the necessary networking required for leadership positions	12 (4.1)	17 (5.8)	45 (15.4)	158 (54.1)	41 (14.0)	19 (6.5)
Women have adequate self-confidence to take leadership positions	10 (3.4)	13 (4.5)	21 (7.2)	167 (57.2)	67 (22.9)	14 (4.8)
Being in a leadership position increases the risk of sexual harassment for women	43 (14.7)	97 (33.2)	37 (12.7)	55 (18.8)	13 (4.5)	47 (16.1)
Having women in leadership positions is acceptable in our culture	28 (9.6)	38 (13.0)	47 (16.1)	138 (47.3)	20 (6.8)	21 (7.2)
Having women in leadership	16 (5.5)	25 (8.6)	46 (15.8)	146 (50.0)	36 (12.3)	23 (7.9)

Statement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	Not Sure
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)

positions is acceptable by religion

Total Respondents = 292

The findings in Table 4 reveal a generally positive perception toward women’s participation in leadership roles despite the presence of cultural and societal barriers. A majority (55.8%) of respondents agreed that families and husbands support women in leadership, while 61% believed that organizational and ministerial structures encourage female leadership. Similarly, 62.3% agreed that women can maintain a healthy work–life balance, and 79.8% affirmed that women possess leadership skills and self-confidence necessary for success.

However, 65.8% acknowledged family and childcare responsibilities as significant barriers to women’s leadership advancement. Additionally, 36.5% believed that leadership roles may expose women to higher risks of sexual harassment, and 30% still viewed women as too emotional for leadership.

Overall, the results indicate that although the social environment in emerging markets is becoming more receptive to women in leadership positions, traditional gender expectations and structural challenges continue to influence their progression.

Table 5: Opportunities for Women to Take a Leadership Position

Statement	Not at all Important	Slightly Important	Moderately Important	Very Important	Extremely Important	Not Sure
	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)	N (%)
Provide leadership training programs specifically designed for women leaders	14 (4.8)	21 (7.2)	25 (8.6)	133 (45.5)	85 (29.1)	14 (4.8)
Offer daycare services for mothers of young children	6 (2.1)	6 (2.1)	18 (6.2)	126 (43.2)	126 (43.2)	10 (3.4)

Statement	Not at all Important N (%)	Slightly Important N (%)	Moderately Important N (%)	Very Important N (%)	Extremely Important N (%)	Not Sure N(%)
Offer mentorship programs	4 (1.4)	12 (4.1)	36 (12.3)	138 (47.3)	84 (28.8)	18 (6.2)
Offer flexible working hours for women	11 (3.8)	19 (6.5)	33 (11.3)	129 (44.2)	87 (29.8)	13 (4.4)
Introduce quotas or representation for women in leadership positions	18 (6.2)	20 (6.8)	45 (15.4)	128 (43.8)	60 (20.5)	21 (7.2)

Total Respondents = 292

Explanation / Discussion:

The findings in Table 5 highlight participants’ strong support for initiatives that promote women’s advancement into leadership positions. The majority of respondents viewed leadership training programs (74.6%), mentorship opportunities (76.1%), and flexible working hours (74%) as either *very important* or *extremely important* strategies for empowering women. Likewise, 86.4% of respondents considered daycare services crucial in helping mothers balance family and professional responsibilities.

However, while 64.3% of respondents favored the introduction of quotas or representation for women in leadership, some participants remained uncertain or only moderately supportive, possibly reflecting mixed cultural or institutional attitudes toward affirmative action measures.

These findings indicate a clear recognition of the need for structured support systems particularly leadership training, mentoring, and family-friendly policies to enhance women’s access to managerial and decision-making positions. The results align with global evidence emphasizing that tailored leadership development and organizational reforms are key levers for breaking the “glass ceiling” and promoting gender equity in leadership.

Table 6: Association Between Women in Leadership Positions and Sociodemographic and Career Characteristics (n = 292)

Variable	In Leadership Position Yes n (%)	Not in Leadership Position No n (%)	P-value
Marital Status			
Single	23 (24.5)	71 (75.5)	0.672
Ever Married	67 (27.3)	177 (72.7)	
Age Group (years)			
≤30	10 (13.0)	67 (87.0)	
31–40	46 (35.7)	83 (64.3)	
>40	34 (28.6)	85 (71.4)	0.001*
Education Level			
School/Diploma	32 (25.0)	96 (75.0)	
College Degree	42 (24.6)	129 (75.4)	
Postgraduate Degree	16 (44.4)	20 (55.6)	0.003*
Profession			
Physician/Dentist/Pharmacist	41 (28.9)	101 (71.1)	
Nurse/Medical Assistant	47 (26.4)	131 (73.6)	0.742
Work Setting			
Directorate of Health	18 (51.4)	17 (48.6)	
Hospital	54 (34.0)	105 (66.0)	
Primary Healthcare Center	18 (22.8)	61 (77.2)	0.024*

*Significant at p < 0.05

As shown in Table 6, women’s participation in leadership roles was significantly associated with age, education level, and work setting ($p < 0.05$). Participants aged 31–40 years (35.7%) and those with postgraduate qualifications (44.4%) were more likely to hold leadership positions than their younger or less educated counterparts. Similarly, those working in directorates of health (51.4%) reported higher leadership representation compared to those in hospitals and primary healthcare centers.

No significant associations were observed between leadership position and marital status or profession ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that while personal demographics may not strongly predict leadership attainment, professional experience, educational advancement, and institutional environment play pivotal roles in women’s ascension to leadership positions in the healthcare sector.

Table 7: Multiple Logistic Regression of Women in Leadership Positions and Sociodemographic and Career Characteristics (n = 292)

Variable	OR	95% CI for OR		P-value
		Lower	Upper	
Age group (years)				
≤30	Ref			
31–40	1.84	0.41	8.22	0.425
>40	3.97	0.79	19.86	0.092
Education level				
School/Diploma	Ref			
College	1.32	0.71	2.46	0.379
Postgraduate	2.74	1.18	6.35	0.020*
Work setting				
Primary Healthcare Center	Ref			
Hospital	1.28	0.64	2.55	0.488
Directorate of Health	4.96	1.97	12.46	<0.001*

Variable	OR	95% CI for OR		P-value
		Lower	Upper	
Received Leadership Training	6.12	2.83	13.23	<0.001*

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

The multiple logistic regression analysis (Table 7) identified education level, work setting, and leadership training as significant predictors of women’s participation in leadership positions.

Women with postgraduate education were 2.7 times more likely (OR = 2.74, $p = 0.020$) to hold leadership positions compared to those with only school or diploma-level education. Similarly, those working in directorates of health had a significantly higher likelihood (OR = 4.96, $p = 0.001$) of occupying leadership roles than those in primary healthcare centers.

Most notably, participants who received formal leadership training were six times more likely (OR = 6.12, $p < 0.001$) to be in leadership positions compared to those without such training.

In contrast, age group and workplace (hospital and Primary Healthcare Center) did not show significant effect. These findings emphasize that professional development opportunities, higher education, and institutional placement strongly influence women’s advancement into leadership roles within the healthcare sector.

Additionally, 27% of the women reported holding leadership positions with the majority of 72.2% serving as heads of units in hospitals and primary healthcare centers. Only a small proportion held higher administrative roles such as directors within health directorates or primary healthcare facilities. Notably, leadership training remained limited as it shows only 13.4%, suggesting that most women acquired their leadership competencies through practical on the job experience rather than formal development programs. These leadership roles typically involved responsibilities such as team supervision, coordination of healthcare services, and participation in administrative decisions, positioning women mainly in middle management rather than top executive levels, where authority and strategic decision making are concentrated. This strong representation is largely attributed to structural and policy driven initiatives including affirmative action, diversity programs and targeted leadership development schemes that actively foster gender equality and empower women to advance into top executive positions.

Majority of participants of about 92.4% reported positive leadership experiences suggesting a favorable self-perception, supportive work environment, or successful leadership outcomes. However, this high rate of positive responses may also reflect social and professional pressures that discourage the acknowledgment of weaknesses or self-doubt. Cultural and workplace norms could contribute to inflated positive evaluations and this potential reporting bias should be considered when interpreting the findings. While the perspectives of participants who had not held

leadership positions were not directly explored in terms of their expectations or concerns, their opinions were indirectly represented through their experiences with female leaders. Future qualitative studies are therefore recommended to gain deeper insight into how both current and aspiring women leaders perceive and articulate their strengths and challenges, particularly in healthcare settings to inform more targeted leadership development programs. Riche et al (2023), opines that low and middle income countries often reveals that women encounter significant barriers in leadership including gender bias and limited opportunities, which contribute to negative experiences. Specifically, Al-Naqbi et al. (2024), found that only 18% of Emirati women were satisfied with their leadership roles while Alabdulazeem et al (2024), reported that merely 15% of female leaders expressed satisfaction with their work environment highlighting the persistent inequalities women face in attaining and sustaining fair leadership positions.

A majority of the study participants (84.6%) reported having experienced a woman in a leadership role at the workplace, with 45.2% evaluating this experience positively. These findings suggest that women's representation in leadership and management positions is visible and increasingly common within healthcare settings, indicating progress in gender representation. However, the level of satisfaction with women in leadership roles still shows room for improvement and further development in leadership practices. But the lack of societal support, particularly regarding institutional frameworks, cultural norms, and social attitudes, remains a significant barrier to women advancing into leadership positions in healthcare. Gendered interpretations of leadership roles can perpetuate biases thereby undermining the recognition of women's capabilities as leaders. These barriers often discourage women from pursuing senior leadership roles or being acknowledged as competent leaders, especially in contexts where leadership has historically been male dominated (Kalaitzi et al, 2019).

From the study, 58.6% of women reported feeling ready to assume leadership roles, indicating that a significant proportion have the confidence to lead. Even when women feel prepared, societal beliefs about gender roles and negative perceptions of their capabilities may lead them to question themselves. While many women perceive themselves as ready for leadership, internalized self-doubt and societal expectations shaped by gender norms and reinforced through social learning can act as both psychological and structural barriers.

Additionally, most participants (80.1%) in this study agreed and strongly agreed that women possess sufficient self-confidence to take on leadership roles. This perception aligns with research examining self-other agreement in leadership ratings, which found that female leaders often receive higher evaluations from others than from themselves. The study also noted that external ratings were positively associated with being female and that agreement between self-ratings and others' ratings was generally stronger for women than men. These findings underscore the importance of encouraging female leaders to recognize their own capabilities, as external perceptions may be more favorable than their self-assessments.

The result reveals that 79.8% of female participants believed that women inherently possess the skills and competencies required for leadership, reflecting strong self-assessment and acknowledgment of leadership potential among women. These findings indicate that women are aware of their own capabilities. However, these results must be interpreted within the cultural and geographical context of Nigeria, where traditional social conventions and gender roles continue to influence women's career trajectories. Social norms often position women as primary caregivers, potentially limiting their availability or perceived suitability for leadership roles, even as awareness of gender equality grows.

The findings of this study are consistent with the role congruity theory of prejudice toward female leaders which posits that women are often perceived as less suitable for leadership due to the mismatch between traditional gender roles and leadership expectations. This theoretical perspective helps explain the societal and institutional biases observed in our data, particularly the tendency to undervalue women's leadership potential and scrutinize their behaviors more critically than men's. Such incongruity contributes to the limited advancement of women in healthcare leadership in Nigeria thereby highlighting the need for systemic change.

5. Conclusion

This study highlights a strong foundation for women's leadership within healthcare settings in Nigeria. A considerable proportion of participants hold leadership roles although these are largely concentrated at lower or middle management levels. Most women in leadership positions reported positive experiences suggesting promising potential for women's advancement in leadership. Additionally, the majority of participants expressed readiness to assume leadership roles, further reinforcing this potential.

A significant number of participants recognized women leaders as capable, citing essential attributes such as self-confidence, leadership skills and strong personalities. This acknowledgment underscores the need to create more opportunities for women in leadership. Employee acceptance of women in leadership and the perception of their success indicate overall support, yet a lack of societal backing remains a major barrier to women's leadership in healthcare.

These findings call for urgent and coordinated action by healthcare institutions and policymakers to dismantle structural and cultural barriers and foster inclusive leadership environments. Implementing structured leadership training programs and childcare support policies can help strengthen women's leadership in Nigeria. Future research should investigate the key barriers and opportunities identified in this study in greater depth using qualitative approaches to provide richer insights into women's experiences in healthcare leadership.

6. Recommendations

Healthcare institutions and policymakers should develop inclusive frameworks and national strategies to support women's progression into senior leadership roles. Appointment and promotion processes must prioritize gender equity and resources should be allocated to facilitate

leadership training and participation in decision making. Support for collaborative coalitions among women leaders is also crucial to advocate for equitable practices and provide mutual support across the healthcare sector.

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